

Azo-triphenylmethane and Azo-pyrone Dyes (Meta Series).

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The present paper deals with azo-triphenylmethane dyestuffs containing azo and triphenylmethane groups in the *meta* position to one another, the object being to study the relative influence of the two chromophores in the *meta* positions as has been done in the case of the *para* positions by previous workers (Green and Sen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, **101**, 1113; Sen and Sett, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **46**, 111; Dutt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **129**, 1171). The *meta* azoaldehydes (A, B, C, D) used in the preparation of the required azotriphenylmethane dyes, have been obtained by coupling salicylaldehyde with the corresponding diazotised amines, of which only (A) seems to have been prepared before (Tummeley, *Annalen*, 1889, **251**, 174; Borsche, *Ber.*, 1900, **33**, 1325).

The above azo-aldehydes have been condensed (i) with dimethyl-aniline and *o*-cresotinic acid to give azo-triphenylcarbinol dyes and (ii) with resorcinol, pyrogallol and diethyl-*m*-aminophenol to give azo-pyrone dyes.

From a comparison of the various azo-triphenylcarbinol and azo-pyrone dyes prepared, it has been found (*vide* Table) that (1) the introduction of one azo group in the *meta* position to the central

carbon atom in a triphenylcarbinol or a pyronine dye is generally attended with an increase in the depth of colour much less than in the case of *para* position ; (2) introduction of a second azo group intensifies that colour still more though to a small extent ; (3) introduction of another triphenylcarbinol group into a molecule containing two azo and one triphenylcarbinol groups is, however, attended with a diminution in the intensity of colour. The leuco condensation products of *o*-cresotinic acid with (C) and (D) are substantive to cotton like the azo-aldehydes themselves, though slightly lighter in colour, while the corresponding carbinols have little or no direct affinity for cotton. Disappearance of the substantive character of the dyestuffs may thus be attributed to the triphenylcarbinol group in its quinonoid form. The other triphenylcarbinol and pyronine dyestuffs derived from (C) and (D) have also no direct affinity for cotton.

A great difference, between the azo-triphenylmethane dyes of the *para* and the *meta* series is that the yellow shade on wool produced by the leuco cresotinic acid compounds of the *para*-series changes from yellow through maroon to dark green and black by after-chroming and the carbinols are remarkably polygenetic (Green and Sen, *loc. cit.*), but the yellow shade produced by the corresponding leuco-compounds in the *meta*-series changed only to olive brown on similar treatment and the carbinols are only feebly polygenetic.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Benzene-azo-salicylaldehyde (A) was prepared by the method of Tummeley (*loc. cit.*), and obtained as golden yellow prisms from dilute alcohol, melting at 127° .

Naphthalene-azo-salicylaldehyde (B).—A solution of diazotised *n*-naphthylamine (14.3 g.) is poured into an alkaline solution of salicylaldehyde (14 g.) and the mixture is stirred for an hour. The precipitated azo compound is filtered, washed and dried. It is obtained as a microcrystalline yellowish orange powder from dil. alcohol. It is soluble in alcohol, ether, benzene, chloroform etc.

The *phenylhydrazone*, prepared in glacial acetic acid solution at the temperature of the water-bath, crystallised from dil. alcohol ; m. p. 96° . (Found : N, 15.01. $C_{23}H_{19}ON_4$, requires N, 15.30 per cent.).

The *oxime* was prepared by adding a strong aqueous solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride and sodium acetate to an alcoholic solution of the aldehyde and heating for 2 hours on the water-bath. The precipitate obtained on dilution is crystallised from dil. alcohol; m. p. 201° (Found: N, 14.68. $C_{11}H_{13}O_2N_3$ requires N, 14.43 per cent.).

Diphenyl-disazo-salicylic acid-salicylaldehyde (C).—A diazotised solution of benzidine (9.2 g.) is added to a cold solution of salicylic acid (7.2 g.) in Na_2CO_3 (23 g.) and 250 c. c. of water. The mixture is stirred for 3-4 hours. The formation of the intermediate compound is complete when the solution no longer gives blue colour with alkaline "H" acid. To this mixture a cold solution of one mol. of salicylaldehyde (6.5 g.) in NaOH is now added and the stirring continued for another 4-5 hours, the completion of the reaction being tested with alkaline β -naphthol. The precipitated azo-compound is then filtered, washed and dried. It is obtained as a micro-crystalline yellowish orange powder from hot nitrobenzene solution. It is insoluble in almost all solvents except nitrobenzene and pyridine.

Oxime.—It was prepared by adding a strong aqueous solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride and sodium acetate to a solution of the aldehyde in pyridine and heating on the water-bath for 3-4 hours. It crystallised from dilute pyridine. It does not melt below 300° . (Found: N, 14.64. $C_{26}H_{19}O_2N_3$ requires N, 14.55 per cent.).

Diphenyl-disazo-bis-salicylaldehyde (D).—A diazotised solution of benzidine (9.2 g.) is poured into a cold solution of salicylaldehyde (6.5 g.) in Na_2CO_3 (23 g.) and water (100 c. c.) and the mixture is stirred for 3-4 hours. When the coupling with one mol. of salicylaldehyde is complete (the mixture being tested as in the above case), a second mol. of salicylaldehyde (6.5 g.) dissolved in the minimum quantity of NaOH solution is added and the stirring continued until the reaction is complete. The precipitated azo compound is filtered, washed and dried. It is obtained as a micro-crystalline yellow powder from hot nitrobenzene solution. It is insoluble in all solvents except nitrobenzene and pyridine.

The *dioxime* was prepared as in the last case. It does not melt below 300° . (Found: N, 17.32. $C_{26}H_{10}O_2N_6$ requires N, 17.5 per cent.).

(5, 6, 7 and 8). *Condensations of the Azo-aldehydes with Dimethylaniline.*

(In the case of a monoaldehyde A, B or C)

(In the case of a dialdehyde D).

One mol. of the aldehyde mixed with the required quantity of dimethylaniline (2 mols. in the case of a monoaldehyde and 4 mols. in the case of a dialdehyde) and a small quantity of conc. HCl is heated for 5-6 hours, at 100° in the case of the aldehydes (A) and (B) and at 120° in the other two cases. The leuco-compound is isolated in the usual way and finally crystallised from chloroform. It is insoluble in ether and benzene, slightly soluble in alcohol and acetone, freely soluble in chloroform.

The leuco compound is oxidised to the carbinol stage by adding lead peroxide to a solution of the former in a mixture of dil. HCl and dil. acetic acid in the cold.

(9, 10, 11 and 12). *Condensations of the Azo-aldehydes with o-Cresotinic Acid.*

(In the case of a monoaldehyde A, B or C)

(In the case of a dialdehyde D)

One mol. of the azo-aldehyde is intimately mixed with the required quantity of dry *o*-cresotic acid (2 mols. in case of a monoaldehyde and 4 mols. in the case of a dialdehyde) and the mixture is dissolved in the minimum quantity of conc. H_2SO_4 (d 1.84). It is kept overnight and then washed with ice-cold water to remove the H_2SO_4 . The product is now dissolved in NaOH solution, filtered, reprecipitated with dil. HCl and again filtered. It is then dried and the finely powdered product is purified by washing with benzene and is finally crystallised from dil. alcohol, when the leuco-compound is obtained as a microcrystalline yellow powder. It is insoluble in ether and benzene, but soluble in alcohol, acetone, chloroform etc.

The carbinol is obtained by condensing the aldehyde with cresotic acid in the cold as above and then adding the requisite quantity of nitrosyl sulphate ($NaNO_2$ dissolved in cold conc. H_2SO_4) to the mixture and heating to $60^\circ-70^\circ$ till the oxidation is complete. The product is then isolated in the manner already described and finally purified by repeated washing with alcohol in which it is insoluble. It may be crystallised from pyridine.

(13, 14, 15 and 16). *Condensations of the Azo-aldehydes with Resorcinol.*

(In the case of a monoaldehyde (In the case of a dialdehyde D)
A, B or C)

One mol. of the aldehyde mixed with resorcinol (2 mols. in the case of a monoaldehyde and 4 mols. in the case of a dialdehyde)

is dissolved in the minimum quantity of conc. H_2SO_4 (d 1.84) and kept at about 120° for 5-6 hours. During the reaction sulphur dioxide is evolved (detected with starch-iodate paper) sulphuric acid acting as condensing as well as oxidising agent. The mixture is cooled and then washed with ice-cold water. The product is then dissolved in NaOH solution, filtered, reprecipitated with dilute HCl, again filtered, washed and dried. The powdered product is then purified by repeated washing with alcohol and other solvents in the case of the products from (A) and (B) and with hot nitrobenzene and ether in the case of the products from (C) and (D), these products being insoluble in all ordinary solvents.

(17, 18, 19 and 20). *Condensations of the Azo-aldehydes with Pyrogallol.*

The method of preparation is similar to that followed in the case of condensation with resocriinol. These compounds are also insoluble in all ordinary solvents.

(21, 22, 23 and 24). *Condensations of the Azo-aldehydes with Diethyl-m-aminophenol.*

(In the case of a monoaldehyde
A, B or C.)

(In the case of a dialdehyde D).

One mol. of the aldehyde mixed with dry diethyl-*m*-aminophenol (2 mols. in the case of a monoaldehyde and 4 mols. in the case of a dialdehyde) is dissolved in the minimum quantity of conc. H_2SO_4 (d 1.84) and kept at about 140° for 6-7 hours. Sulphur dioxide being evolved during the course of the reaction. The mixture is allowed to cool and extracted with cold water. To the filtered aqueous solution ammonium hydrate is added and the precipitate is filtered, washed and dried. It is then purified by washing with benzene and finally crystallised from dil. alcohol. It is insoluble in ether and benzene, but soluble in alcohol, acetone, chloroform and nitrobenzene.

The properties and analyses of the compounds prepared and studied are given in the annexed table,

TABLE.

Names of compounds.	Melting point.	Analysis : P.c. of N.	Shade on wool and silk.	REMARKS.	
Azo-aldehyde.	Found.	Calc.			
1. A.	127°	—	Yellow		
2. B.	151°	10·23	10·14	Yellowish orange.	
3. C.	Does not melt below 300°	12·12	12·02	} Also substantive to cotton.	
4. D.	Do.	13·23	13·44		
Cond. products (eneco) of dimethyl- aniline with the azo-aldehydes.					
5. A.	Melts with decomposition.	—	—	} No. 5 prepared before by Dutt (loc.cit.). Shades produced by carbinols. These also dye tanned cotton. 7 and 8 have no direct affinity for cotton like the mother substances C & D.	
6. B.	"	10·81	10·20		Greenish blue
7. C.	"	11·66	12·17		Green
8. D.	"	12·11	12·47		Greenish blue
1. Benzene-azo-salicylaldehyde;					
2. Naphthalene-1-azo-salicylaldehyde;					
3. Diphenyl-diazo-salicylic acid-salicylaldehyde;					
4. Diphenyl-diazo-bi-salicylaldehyde;					
5. Benzene-azo-5-hydroxy-8 : 13-tetramethyldiamino-triphenyl-methane;					
6. Naphthalene-azo-5-hydroxy-8 : 13-tetramethyldiamino-triphenyl-methane;					
7. Diphenyl-diazo-salicylic acid-5-hydroxy-8 : 13-tetramethyldiaminotriphenylmethane;					
8. Diphenyl-diazo-bi-(6-hydroxy-8 : 13-tetramethyldiamino-triphenylmethane);					

Names of compounds.	Melting point.	Analysis : P.c. of N.		Shade on wool and silk.	REMARKS.
		Found.	Calc.		
Cond. products (leuco) of <i>o</i> -cresotic acid with the azo-aldehydes.					Shades produced by carbinols. The corresponding carbinols in the <i>para</i> -series (Green and Sen, <i>loc. cit.</i>) produce red shades. All the carbinols are feebly polygenetic. The leuco compounds produce shades similar to the aldehydes. The leuco compounds 11 & 12 are like the mother substances C & D substitutive to cotton but their carbinols have little or no direct affinity for cotton.
9. A.	212°	5.24	5.47	Reddish orange.	
10. B.	159°	4.71	4.98	" "	
11. C.	Does not melt below 300°.	7.52	7.45	" "	
12. D.	Do.	5.13	5.48	" "	
Cond. products of resorcinol with the azo-aldehydes.					Alkaline solutions feebly fluorescent. Resorcinol-1'-hydroxybenzene (Sen & Sinha, <i>J. Am. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1923, 45, 2984) produces only orange shades and its alkaline solution is strongly fluorescent thus the azo-group in the <i>meta</i> position increases the depth of colour but diminishes fluorescence. 15 slightly deeper than 13. 16 is slightly higher than 15. 15 & 16 unlike C & D have no direct affinity for cotton.
13. A.	Does not melt below 300°.	6.15	6.86	Brownish red	
14. B.	Do.	5.79	6.11	Red	
15. C.	Do.	8.14	8.64	Brownish red	
16. D.	Do.	6.24	6.88	Brown	
9. Benzeneazo-5 : 8 : 13-trihydroxy-9 : 12-dimethyl-7 : 14-dicarboxytriphenylmethane;					
10. 2-Naphthalene- α -azo-5 : 8 : 13-trihydroxy-9 : 12-dimethyl-7 : 14-dicarboxy-triphenylmethane;					
11. Diphenyl-diazo-salicylic acid-5 : 8 : 13-trihydroxy-9 : 12-dimethyl-7 : 14-dicarboxy-triphenylmethane;					
12. Diphenyl-diazo-bi-(5 : 8 : 13-trihydroxy-9 : 12-dimethyl-7 : 14-dicarboxy-triphenylmethane);					
13. Benzene-azo-resorcinol-salicycin;					14. Naphthalene- α -azo-resorcinol-salicycin;
15. Diphenyl-diazo-salicylic acid-resorcinol-salicycin;					15. Diphenyl-diazo-bi-resorcinol-salicycin;

Names of compounds.	Melting point.	Analysis : P. c. of N.		Shade on wool and silk.	REMARKS.
		Found.	Calc.		
Cond. products of pyrogallol with the azo-aldehydes.					
17. A.	Does not melt below 300°.	5.69	6.86	Greyish black	Shades on iron-mordanted wool. All feebly polygenetic. 19 & 20 unlike C & D have no direct affinity for cotton.
18. B.	Do.	5.20	5.71	"	
19. C.	Do.	—	—	"	
20. D.	Do.	—	—	"	
Cond. products of diethyl- <i>m</i> -amino-phenol with the azo-aldehydes.					
21. A.	185°	9.89	10.45	Violet	Also dye tanned cotton. 23 slightly deeper than 21. 24 slightly lighter than 23. 23 & 24 unlike C & D have no direct affinity for cotton.
22. B.	Does not melt below 300°.	9.10	9.56	Bluish violet	
23. C.	Do.	10.56	10.82	"	
24. D.	Do.	10.08	10.47	Violet	
17. Benzene-azo-pyrogallol salicetin ;					
18. Naphthalene- <i>α</i> -azo-pyrogallol-salicetin ;					
19. Diphenyl-diazo-salicylic acid-resorcinol-salicetin ;					
20. Diphenyl-diazo-diethyl- <i>m</i> -aminophenol-salicetin ;					
21. Benzene-azo-diethyl- <i>m</i> -aminophenol-salicetin ;					
22. Naphthalene- <i>α</i> -azo-diethyl- <i>m</i> -aminophenol-salicetin ;					
23. Diphenyl-diazo-salicylic acid-diethyl- <i>m</i> -aminophenol-salicetin ;					
24. Diphenyl-diazo-bi-(diethyl- <i>m</i> -aminophenol-salicetin). (The compounds have been named according to the system of nomenclature used in "Systematic Survey of Organic Colouring Matters" by Green).					

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